

ADOPTION OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOL IN THE INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES FOR STUDENTS' DEVELOPMENT IN MAGUINDANAO PROVINCE, PHILIPPINES

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Adoption of Public and Private School in the Instructional Strategies for Students' Development in Maguindanao Province, Philippines

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Abstract

Generally, this study was determining the public and private school instructional strategies in the adoption of student's confidence development in Maguindanao province, specifically, this aims to answer the following questions, what are the profile of the respondents in terms of regular school is in, gender, age and length of service, general education, and position/ designation and employment status? What are the public and private school instructional strategies in the adoption of students' confidence in development as follows, adopting learning style, flexible instruction, learning preparedness, learning support, mental ability, self-Esteem, skill competency, is there a significant relationship between instruction strategies and students' confidence development, is there any significant influence on instructional strategies and students' confidence development. Survey questionnaire prepared by the researcher and simple computations in percent's mean and test of relationship among variables was used in this study. The extent of the teachers' teaching strategies in the schools of Maguindanao were described as follows adopting learning style, learning preparedness and learning support were as moderately implemented and in the students' confidence development is the mental ability were the description of moderately implemented the general mean is 2.641 as moderately implemented the teaching strategies to the learning of the students in an instructional strategies that students adopting through self- confidence development the students. Teacher as part of their job must examine test result of their students to discover teaching strategies so that they could be used to improve instructional delivery and learning in the school system. The school should be provided by appropriate scientific interventions in terms of sustainable training to develop the capacity building and enhancement of faculty productivity to cope with the new trend in learning strategies to improve and maximize the teaching-learning process. A similar study should be replicated using the different variables that would affect and enhance students learning capability particular in adopting learning styles and others strategies that be ready to apply in learning skills and also in same variables that influence the academic performance of the students in learning.

Keywords: *development, adoption, strategies, instructional*

Introduction

Adoptive learning is one technique for providing personalized learning, which aims to provide efficient, effective, and customized learning paths to engage each student. Adaptive learning systems use a data-drive approach to adjust the path and pace of learning, enabling the delivery of personalized learning at scale. (January 4, 2017).

The teacher directs students in the conventional and procedural use of technology tools. At the adoption level, technology tools are used in conventional ways. The teacher makes decisions about which technology tool to use and when and how to use it.

Instructional strategies are techniques of teachers use to help students become independent, strategic learners. These strategies become learning strategies when students independently select the appropriate ones and use them effectively to accomplish tasks or meet goals.

According to Derrick Meador, on July 23, 2019, instructional strategies include all approaches that a teachers may take to engage students in the learning process activity. These strategies drive a teacher's instruction as they work to meet specific learning objectives and ensure that their students are equipped with the tools they need to be successful. Effective instructional strategies meet all learning styles and the developmental needs of all learners. Teachers must be equipped with a well-rounded arsenal of effective instructional strategies to maximize their effectiveness and to increase student learning opportunities.

In an engagement of students is essential for their learning. In order to maintain interest in, achieve a working knowledge of, and eventually master a subject or concept, students need opportunities and environments that support reflection, practice, constructive feedback and collaboration. These engagement strategies are explored whether you are looking for feedback on your teaching from your students in the midst of the semester or making sense of your course evaluations or looking for a colleague to come into your class to observe.

Educators who use instructional strategies allow students to make meaningful connections between concepts learned in class and real-life situations. They offer an opportunity for students to demonstrate their knowledge and course correct on their own when needed. The seven effective teaching strategies for the classroom like visualization, cooperative learning, inquiry-based instruction, and differentiation, technology in the classroom, behavior management and professional development.

Modelling is an instructional strategy in which the teacher demonstrates a new concept or approach to learning and students learn by observing. Whenever a teacher demonstrates a concept for student, that teacher is modelling.

Research Questions

Generally, this study will be determining the adoption of public and private school instructional strategies for students' development in Maguindanao Province. Specifically, this aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Appointment Status
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Age
 - 1.4. Length of service
 - 1.5. Educational Attainment
 - 1.6. Position / designation
2. To what extent the students' adaptation of instructional strategies in terms of:
 - 2.1. Adopting learning style
 - 2.2. Flexible instruction
 - 2.3. Learning preparedness
 - 2.4. Learning support
3. To what extent in the students' development in terms of:
 - 3.1. Knowledge
 - 3.2. Self-Esteem
 - 3.3. Skills competency
4. Is there any significant relationship between respondents profile and the students' development?
5. Is there any significant relationship between the students' instructional strategies adaptation and students' development?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive – correlation research design. Descriptive was used to describe the extent of adaptation of the instructional strategies and the students development. Correlation was used to see the relationship of the respondent variable and the student variable.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 130 teachers who had been serving at least four (4) years in service as faculty member. They were selected as respondents based on the service rendered regardless of gender.

A sample procedure used in this research study was simple random sampling techniques considering the large size of the target population of the respondents in the Maguindanao province. The researcher used the Slorin's formula in getting the sample/ respondents of this study.

Instrument

The researcher made use of a modified questionnaires which are divided into three (3) parts;

Part I use the profile of the respondents that includes the appointment status, the Gender, Age, Length of Service, Educational Attainment, Position / Designation. Part II was the instructional strategies and Part III was the students' development.

The data gathered was summarized using the frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The descriptive – correlation research was used to determine the adoption of public and private schools instructional strategies for students' development in Maguindanao province as perceptions of the different respondents on the teachers' adoption of public and private schools instructional strategies for students' development in Maguindanao province.

This study was adoption of public and private schools instructional strategies for students' development in Maguindanao province.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings on the adoption of public and private school instructional strategies for students' development in Maguindanao province for the school year 2021-2022.

The Profile Of The Respondents

The teachers' occupies a profile to know the status of the respondents in the level of education especially on the individual identification. It also shown on this table that the school are found and other background profile of the respondents of this study.

This table 1 shown the frequency and percentage rating of the respondents in terms of gender indicated to the questionnaire. As shown in the table, 67 or 51.54 percent were female, 63 or 48.46 percent were male. The finding implies that majority of the respondents were female in Maguindanao 1 and 2 division. This implies that most of the teachers in Maguindanao are female.

Table 1. *The Respondents Ratings Of Teachers' Profile In According To Their Gender*

<i>Indicators Item</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	63	48.46 %
Female	67	51.54 %
Total	130	100 %

Table 2 shows that out of 130 respondents, 45 or 34.62 percent were at age bracket of 20-29 years old, 43 or 33.07 percent were at the age bracket of 40 – 49 years old and 42 or 32.31 percent were at age of bracket 30-39 years old.

Table 2. *The Respondents Indicator In Their Age*

<i>Age Bracket</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
20- 29	45	34.62 %
30- 39	42	32.31 %
40 - 49	43	33.07 %
Total	130	100 %

It implies that most of the teachers in Maguindanao is relatively young in 12 Maguindanao. Implies further the tardiness are still energetic enough to the responsibility to a teacher in adding this given young.

Table 3. *The Respondents Indicators In According To Their Civil Status*

<i>Civil Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single	76	58.46 %
Married	47	36.15 %
Widow	0	00.00 %
Separated	7	5.38 %
Total	130	99.99 %

Table 3 shows that majority 76 or 58.46 percent of the respondents were still single, 47 or 36.15 percent were married and only 7 or 5.38 percent were separated. It implies that majority of the respondents were actively participated and can be there function since most of them are still single.

Table 4. *The Respondents Indicators In According To Their General Education*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
BEED	20	15.38 %
BSED	86	66.15 %
MA	20	15.38 %
DOCTORAL	4	3.09 %
Total	130	100 %

Table 4 shows that majority 86 or 66.15 percent of the respondents were BSEd graduate, 20 or 15.38 percent were master's degree and BEED degree and 4 or 3.09 percent were holder of Doctoral degree.

It implies that majority of the respondents were graduate of both BSEd and BEED and only 20 or 15.38 percent were masters and 4 or 3.09 percent were Doctors degree.

Table 5. *The Respondents Indicators In According To Their Length Of Service*

<i>Length Of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1 - 3	20	15.38 %
4 - 6	35	26.92 %
7 – 9	46	35.38 %
10 - 12	29	22.31 %
Total	130	99.99 %

Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents 46 or 35.38 percent were 7 to 9 years of teaching service experience, 35 or 26.92 percent were 4 to 6 years in service and 29 or 22.32 percent were 10 to 12 years in service experience in teaching and 20 or 15.38 percent were at least than 1 to 3 years in service. It implies that most of the respondents were still new in the service. It suffice to their age which are relatively young.

Table 6 shows that majority 78 or 60.00 percent of the respondents were classroom adviser, 27 or 20.77 percent were relieving teachers and 25 or 19.23 percent were school administrators. It implies that most of the respondents were classroom teachers both adviser and relieving teachers respectively only 25 or 19.23 percent were school administrators. It implies that most of the respondents applying teaching in their students is the classroom teachers' advisers.

Table 6. *The Respondents Indicators In According To Their Position / Designation*

<i>Designation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Classroom Adviser	78	60.00 %
Relieving Teachers	27	20.77 %
School Administrators	25	19.23 %
Total	130	100 %

Table 7 shows that majority 78 or 60.00 percent of the respondents were permanent, 30 or 23.08 percent were contractual and 12 or 9.23 percent were volunteer teachers, 10 or 7.69 percent were provisional. It implies that most of the respondents were permanent either contractual and volunteer perspective only 10 or 7.69 percent were provisional in appointment.

Table 7. *The Respondents Indicators In According To Their Employment Status*

<i>Status Of Appointment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Permanent	78	60.00 %
Provisional	10	7.69 %
Contractual	30	23.08 %
Volunteer	12	9.23 %
Total	130	100 %

Teachers' Instructional Strategies

The teacher occupies a strategic position in the teaching learning process. To become effective, teachers must be equipped with best teaching practices such as procedures, strategies, methods and approaches in presenting, implementing and assessing classroom instruction in according with the objective set (De Guzman, Z.D, 1998)

Table 8. *Instructional Strategies In Terms Of Adopting Learning Style*

<i>Adopting Learning Style</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Focuses on knowledge development and curriculum implementation	2.0	Less Implemented	3.20	Moderately Implemented
2. Employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores.	3.29	Moderately Implemented	3.33	Moderately Implemented
3. Gives illustrations or examples that make lessons clear	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.33	Moderately Implemented
4. Modifies and enriches curriculum based on the learners' needs	2.03	Less implemented	3.38	Moderately Implemented
5. Emphasizes the importance of participating in online classes, collaborative learning, and formative assessment such as quizzes and tests, exercises and homework	2.0	Less Implemented	3.30	Moderately Implemented
6. Applies knowledge of content that improves learner performance in math areas	3.38	Moderately Implemented	3.38	Moderately Implemented
7. Builds optimal individual learning paths as sequences of modules	3.38	Moderately Implemented	3.37	Moderately Implemented
8. Develops individual learnings and support students' engagement so their potential and success are maximized	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.26	Moderately Implemented
9. Support learners' acquisition skills through diversification of teaching paths and personalization as an achievement cognitive excellence.	3.22	Moderately Implemented	3.25	Moderately Implemented
10. Recognize students' needs and provide them with the most appropriate didactic activities.	3.42	Moderately Implemented	3.22	Moderately Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.933	Moderately Implemented	3.302	Moderately Implemented

Table 8 shows the rating of the respondents in mean and the interpretation of the data based on the result of teachers' strategies in terms of adopting learning style, the statement number 1 got the highest mean of 3.42 that stated in this item recognize students' needs and provide them with the most appropriate didactic activities with the description of moderately implemented, it implies the most of the teachers in public schools were adopting strategies in the table numbers 6 and 7 in their statement in the public school got the highest mean of 3.38 that applies knowledge of content that improves learner performance in math areas and builds optimal individual learning paths as sequences of modules with the description of moderately implemented.

According to Derrick Meador, on July 23, 2019, Instructional strategies provide teachers with the flexibility necessary to meet individual learning needs. The sheer number of instructional strategies at a teacher's disposal provides the flexibility to differentiate instruction. In the statement number 2 got the mean of 3.29 with stated that employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores with the description of moderately implemented it implies that the teachers applied in teaching strategies through

the low average score students.

in the number 8 statement got the mean of 3.28 this was stated develops individual learnings and support students' engagement so their potential and success are maximized according to Saskatchewan (2021), education considers that there are five categories of instructional strategies. This strategy fosters the development of individual student initiative, self-reliance and self-improvement. Independent study may also involve learning in peer partnership or as part of a small group.

Statement number 3 got the mean of 3.33 that stated gives illustrations or examples that make lessons clear, the support learners' acquisition skills through diversification of teaching paths and personalization as an achievement cognitive excellence got the mean of 3.22 with the description of moderately implemented according to the learning supports, stated are the resources, strategies and practices that provide physical, social, emotional, and intellectual supports intended to enable all pupils to have equal opportunity for success at school by addressing barriers to and promoting engagement in learning and teaching.

In the statement number 1 and 5 were as the statement is emphasizes the importance of participating in online classes, collaborative learning, and formative assessment such as quizzes and tests, exercises and homework and focuses on knowledge development and curriculum implementation were got the lowest rating of mean of 2.0 based on the evaluation of the teachers in adopting learning style of the instructional strategies for the students because according to the respondents in public teachers did not focus on what did explained by the teacher they make their own skills or likes.

In the private school based on the given rating on the adopting learning style is the highest mean were as the statement number 4 and 6 got the 3.38 were mean that statement were are modifies and enriches curriculum based on the learners' needs and applies knowledge of content that improves learner performance in math areas according to Derrick Meador, effective instructional strategies meet all learning styles and the developmental needs of all learners.

The statement number 7 got the mean of 3.37 stated that builds optimal individual learning paths as sequences of modules, the number 2 and 3 got the mean of 3.33 were the statement are gives illustrations or examples that make lessons clear and employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores. The statement number 5 were is the mean of 3.30 that the statement is emphasizes the importance of participating in online classes, collaborative learning, and formative assessment such as quizzes and tests, exercises and homework the next statement is the develops individual learnings and support students' engagement so their potential and success are maximized were as the mean is 3.26, support learners' acquisition skills through diversification of teaching paths and personalization as an achievement cognitive excellence were the mean of 3.25, the statement number 10 were got the mean of 3.22 that stated in recognize students' needs and provide them with the most appropriate didactic activities.

And the lowest mean were are 3.20 with the number 1 statement is focuses on knowledge development and curriculum implementation but the description is moderately implemented meaning both public and private school are different adopting of learning style in teaching of the students especially in instructional strategies.

It implies that mostly adopting learning style of the teacher are applies knowledge of content that improves learner performance in math areas, builds optimal individual learning paths as sequences of modules and others items and only were 2.0 mean that focuses on knowledge development and curriculum implementation, emphasizes the importance of participating in online classes, collaborative learning, and formative assessment such as quizzes and tests, exercise and homework were less implemented.

Table 9. *Instructional Strategies In Terms Of Flexible Instruction*

<i>Flexible Instruction</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Includes explanations and demonstrations of teaching materials and the organization of learning activities.	2.01	Less Implemented	3.22	Moderately Implemented
2. Use a range of instructional strategies that improve learner performances.	2.01	Less Implemented	2.02	Less Implemented
3. Uses differentiated appropriate learning to address needs and interests.	1.99	Less Implemented	3.23	Moderately Implemented
4. Uses appropriated teaching as instructions to address learning goals.	2.0	Less Implemented	3.20	Moderately Implemented
5. Employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
6. Enhance learning relevance and efficacy through both school provided and personal technology	2.0	Less Implemented	3.21	Moderately Implemented
7. Acquires new or modifies and reinforces existing, knowledge, behavior, skills, values, or preferences and may involve synthesizing different types of information.	2.0	Less Implemented	3.25	Moderately Implemented
8. Prepares a flexible learning schedule to find the new learning design in the classroom process.	2.01	Less Implemented	3.35	Moderately Implemented
9. Collects information from the students about the flexible	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented

learning design in the classroom environment.				
10. Plan activities according to learners interests and enthusiasm	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.002	Less Implemented	2.748	Moderately Implemented

In this table shows that in public school implemented in teaching flexible instruction of the indicators base on the respondents that highest statement mean 2.01 were stated in the number 1 includes explanations and demonstrations of teaching materials and the organization of learning activities, use a range of instructional strategies that improve learner performances, and statement number 8 were it including the prepares a flexible learning schedule to find the new learning design in the classroom process, statement number 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10 were mean 2.0 uses appropriated teaching as instructions to address learning goals, employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores, enhance learning relevance and efficacy through both school provided and personal technology, acquires new or modifies and reinforces existing, knowledge, behavior, skills, values, or preferences and may involve synthesizing different types of information, collects information from the students about the flexible learning design in the classroom environment and the statement number 10 were plan activities according to learners interests and enthusiasm were the description of less implemented only number 3 item that were mean of 1.99 that stated with uses differentiated appropriate learning to address needs and interests were the description of less implemented. It implies that in the public school less implementation in flexible instruction to uses in teaching to the students.

In private school indicators of the respondents responses on the questionnaire give the highest item got mean of 3.35 in the item number 8 stated that prepares a flexible learning schedule to find the new learning design in the classroom process, number 7 items were mean 3.25 stated that acquires new or modifies and reinforces existing, knowledge, behavior, skills, values, or preferences and may involve synthesizing different types of information, number 3 items were mean of 3.23.

That the statement is an uses differentiated appropriate learning to address needs and interests, number 1 were mean of 3.22 that includes explanations and demonstrations of teaching materials and the organization of learning activities, number 6 items were mean of 3.21 that enhance learning relevance and efficacy through both school provided and personal technology, number 4 were mean of 3.20.

That uses appropriated teaching as instructions to address learning goals were the descriptive of moderately implemented in adopting teaching flexible instruction to the students learning style. But in the items number 2 were mean of 2.02 that they stated a use a range of instructional strategies that improve learner performances, the number 5, 9 and 10 were got the lowest mean of 2.0 that stated in employs differentiated learning applied to learners with low average scores, collects information from the students about the flexible learning design in the classroom environment and plan activities according to learners interests and enthusiasm were the description of less implemented.

It implies that most of the respondents apply in teaching flexible instruction or adopting in teaching style in private school but some items were mean of 2.0 less implemented in teaching of flexible instruction in to the students. That it implies the public and private school are less implemented in flexible instructional according to Coastal Carolina (2022) active learning engages students in activities beyond reading, listening or watching to deepen their learning and connection with the material. Students engaged in active learning often are: talking with each other in small groups or large discussions. Developing skills rather than memorizing information. (Page 35, RRL).

Table 10. *Instructional Strategies In Terms Of Learning Preparedness*

<i>Learning Preparedness</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Prepares strategies and policies that must be ongoing and self-sustaining to be effective	3.42	Moderately Implemented	3.45	Moderately Implemented
2. Develop and leverage youth-targeted preparedness curricula that are designed specifically, to meet children’s educational needs.	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
3. Build learner’s preparedness programs that contribute to overall school community preparedness goals	3.29	Moderately Implemented	3.27	Moderately Implemented
4. Supports the implementation of learners’ preparedness learning programs	2.03	Less Implemented	3.12	Moderately Implemented
5. Organize a plan and program that meets the needs of the learners	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
6. Provides learning opportunities that support the extension of knowledge in learning.	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.36	Moderately Implemented
7. Delegates more operations to their administrative staff to free up their time for strategic school needs.	3.21	Moderately Implemented	3.20	Moderately Implemented
8. Support the need of learners for more advanced technology development that considers the different levels of learning.	2.0	Less Implemented	3.24	Moderately Implemented

9. Consider the students' needs like resources and materials to ensure students' academic success.	3.24	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
10. Consider various strategies to teach well and consider best practices for engaging learners through different platform.	2.04	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.922	Moderately Implemented	3.166	Moderately Implemented

In this table shows that in public school implemented in teaching in learning preparedness, were most of the items were moderately implemented from item number 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 9, and 7 that were statement emphasizes that in teaching learning preparedness e prepares strategies and policies that must be ongoing and self-sustaining to be effective, develop and leverage youth-targeted preparedness curricula that are designed specifically, to meet children's educational needs, provides learning opportunities that support the extension of knowledge in learning, organize a plan and program that meets the needs of the learners, build learner's preparedness programs that contribute to overall school community preparedness goals, consider the students' needs like resources and materials to ensure students' academic success, delegates more operations to their administrative staff to free up their time for strategic school needs, consider various strategies to teach well and consider best practices for engaging learners through different platform, supports the implementation of learners' preparedness learning programs, support the need of learners for more advanced technology development that considers the different levels of learning in the public school where are the mean is 3.42, 3.33, 3.29, 3.24, 3.21 with the description of moderately implemented, and the 3 items are mean of 2.04, 2.03 and 2.0 with the description of less implemented this was the public school in adopting instructional learning preparedness.

In the private school were as the following items are got highest mean in items number 1 stated prepares strategies and policies that must be ongoing and self-sustaining to be effective were the mean of 3.45 us moderately implemented, in number 6 were stated that provides learning opportunities that support the extension of knowledge in learning were the mean 3.36, the number 9, 5 and 2 items stated that consider the students' needs like resources and materials to ensure students' academic success, organize a plan and program that meets the needs of the learners, and develop and leverage youth-targeted preparedness curricula that are designed specifically, to meet children's educational needs were are the mean of 3.34 with the description of moderately, in the number 3 were stated that build learner's preparedness programs that contribute to overall school community preparedness goals were as the mean of 3.27 with the description of moderately implemented, number 8 were stated that support the need of learners for more advanced technology development that considers the different levels of learning were the mean of 3.24 with the description of moderately implemented, number 7 stated that delegates more operations to their administrative staff to free up their time for strategic school needs were as the 3.20 with the description of the moderately implemented, number 4 stated that supports the implementation of learners' preparedness learning programs were as mean 3.12 with the description of moderately implemented, the number 10 item were lowest mean that stated consider various strategies to teach well and consider best practices for engaging learners through different platform were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented.

It implies that public and private school mostly implemented the learning preparedness of the students in adopting learning style in terms of teaching strategies prospectively that lowest mean in the public school were 2.0 that number 8 stated that support the need of learners for more advanced technology development that considers the different levels of learning but in the private school were 2.0 is the number 10 that consider various strategies to teach well and consider best practices for engaging learners through different platform meaning is we need to practice this both public and private school that we focus on this strategies of learning preparedness for the students,

According to this statement independent study is a form of education offered by many high schools, colleges, and other educational institutions. It is sometimes referred to as directed study, and is an educational activity undertaken by an individual with little to no supervision. Tips for independent study, create a designated study space, mute your phone, create an effective study schedule, establish a reward system, make your work efficient, vary your study techniques, use efficient revision techniques, time yourself.

Table 11. *Instructional Strategies In Terms Of Learning Support*

<i>Learning Support</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Use visual presentation, graphics, videos and slides during class presentation.	3.43	Moderately Implemented	3.42	Moderately Implemented
2. Applies lessons that recognize multiple intelligence and value the learning strength of the learners.	3.20	Moderately Implemented	3.25	Moderately Implemented
3. Develops and selects appropriate and varied learning resources that accommodate different learning style and preferences.	3.24	Moderately Implemented	3.24	Moderately Implemented
4. Use cooperative learnings to develop skills among others.	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
5. Integrates interpersonal skills, communications, teamwork and decision making.	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.29	Moderately Implemented
6. Uses of specific methodology for supplementary teaching in English and Mathematics.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented

7. Identifies pupils experiencing low achievement and/or learning difficulties and the implementation of structured procedures for diagnostic assessment.	3.22	Moderately Implemented	3.23	Moderately Implemented
8. Supplement teaching based on the outcomes of diagnostic assessment.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
9. Demonstrates leadership, management, mentoring, and coaching skills, as well as knowledge of administrative qualities and procedures.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
10. Drafts and develop learning assessment activities that align with learning goals and objectives.	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.922	Moderately Implemented	3.166	Moderately Implemented

In this table shows that in public school implemented in teaching in learning support, were in the number 1 item is a highest got mean into the respondents in use visual presentation, graphics, videos and slides during class presentation, in the number 10 items were stated in drafts and develop learning assessment activities that align with learning goals and objectives, in item number 5 were stated integrates interpersonal skills, communications, teamwork and decision making, were number 7 items stated that identifies pupils experiencing low achievement and/or learning difficulties and the implementation of structured procedures for diagnostic assessment, and the items number 2 stated that applies lessons that recognize multiple intelligence and value the learning strength of the learners, were are the mean of the following into highest mean 3.43, 3.33, 3.33, 3.28, 3.24, 3.22, 3.20, description of moderately implemented the items number 6 uses of specific methodology for supplementary teaching in English and Mathematics, in the number 9 were are the mean of with the items number 8 supplement teaching based on the outcomes of diagnostic assessment were mean is 2.0 based on the result in the table shows with the description of less implemented.

In private school in using the learning support in item number 1 were the highest mean in use visual presentation, graphics, videos and slides during class presentation were the mean of 3.42 with the description of moderately implemented, in number 10 and 4 were mean of 3.34 drafts and develop learning assessment activities that align with learning goals and objectives, use cooperative learning to develop skills among others with the description of moderately implemented, number 5 items were stated in an integrates interpersonal skills, communications, teamwork and decision making were the mean of 3.29, and number 2 items applies lessons that recognize multiple intelligence and value the learning strength of the learners were the mean of 3.25 with the description of moderately implemented, item number 3 were develops and selects appropriate and varied learning resources that accommodate different learning style and preferences were the mean of 3.24, in the number 7 is an identifies pupils experiencing low achievement and/or learning difficulties and the implementation of structured procedures for diagnostic assessment were the mean of 3.23 with the description of moderately implemented, in the item number 9, 8 and 6 were stated in demonstrates leadership, management, mentoring, and coaching skills, as well as knowledge of administrative qualities and procedures, supplement teaching based on the outcomes of diagnostic assessment, uses of specific methodology for supplementary teaching in English and Mathematics were the mean of 2.0 with the description of the less implemented.

It implies that most of the learning support in teaching and strategies are applied the public and private school in the item number 9, 8 and 6 were stated in demonstrates leadership, management, mentoring, and coaching skills, as well as knowledge of administrative qualities and procedures, supplement teaching based on the outcomes of diagnostic assessment, uses of specific methodology for supplementary teaching in English and Mathematics were the mean of 2.0 with the description of the less implemented meaning it will be less implemented the teachers both teachers of the public and private school.

According to this statement supposed to be it will come in learning supports are the resources, strategies and practices that provide physical, social, emotional, and intellectual supports intended to enable all pupils to have equal opportunity for success at school by addressing barriers to and promoting engagement in learning and teaching. (Page 39, RRL).

Students' Development

As teachers, they must be imbued with values, attitudes and dispositions that foster a classroom atmosphere of mutual trust of individual characteristics, especially on students' needs, interest and abilities (Salandanan, 2005).

The improvement of classroom teaching is dependent solely on teacher competencies and obtaining a better academic performance depends upon several factors such as mental ability, self-esteem, and skill competency. According to Buston and Espiritu (1996) asserted that teachers must have to update knowledge of new concept, approaches, methodologies, techniques and strategies for effective learning process. This was including public and private school strategies and development of the students as follow items interpreted.

Table 12 shows that mostly in the respondents on the students' development in Knowledge ability or knowledge were represent in this table the rating in the highest mean of each items indicators in the questionnaire based on result, as you notice in public school in number 10, 5 and 6 were stated can openly address their questions without fear of being judged, select, organize, and integrate ideas in general academic problem-solving ideas, develop numerous habits, information, attitudes, and experiences that are known as learning, and understands to play a more active role in their active role in their learning, were the mean of 3.28, item number 9 can master state-

defined content standards in core academic subjects were the mean of 3.24, in the number 2 equips knowledge and skills in terms of thinking critically, and solving complex problems were the mean of 3.20, were the descriptive of moderately implemented.

Table 12. *Students' Development In Terms Of Knowledge Ability*

<i>Knowledge The Teachers Observe The Learners That...</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Improves in academic performance in terms of analytic	1.99	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
2. Equips knowledge and skills in terms of thinking critically, and solving complex problems.	3.20	Moderately Implemented	3.21	Moderately Implemented
3. Understands to play a more active role in their active role in their learning.	3.24	Moderately Implemented	3.26	Moderately Implemented
4. Capacitate mental ability in terms of ideas and comprehend abstract problems.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
5. Select, organize, and integrate ideas in general academic problem-solving ideas.	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.27	Moderately Implemented
6. Develop numerous habits, information, attitudes, and experiences that are known as learning.	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.28	Moderately Implemented
7. Recognize capacity to learn and recall information, ideas reactions, and adapt the information to their behavior.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.10	Less Implemented
8. Evaluates specific constructs such as linguistic, mechanical, numerical, social, and unique skills included in general mental ability tests	2.0	Less Implemented	2.09	Less Implemented
9. Can master state-defined content standards in core academic subjects.	3.24	Moderately Implemented	3.24	Moderately Implemented
10. Can openly address their questions without fear of being judged.	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.29	Moderately Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.751	Moderately Implemented	2.774	Moderately Implemented

In the number 4, 7 and 8 were stated in capacitate mental ability in terms of ideas and comprehend abstract problems, recognize capacity to learn and recall information, ideas reactions, and adapt the information to their behavior, evaluates specific constructs such as linguistic, mechanical, numerical, social, and unique skills included in general mental ability tests, were the mean of 2.0, were the number 1 item indicator were mean of 1.99 with the mean of less implemented.

In the private school, number 10, is a highest mean of 3.29 it can openly address their questions without fear of being judged, follow the number 6 items were stated in the develop numerous habits, information, attitudes, and experiences that are known as learning were the mean of 3.28, the number 5 were stated in select, organize, and integrate ideas in general academic problem-solving ideas were the mean of 3.27 with the description of moderately implemented, the item number 3 is to understands to play a more active role in their active role in their learning were the mean of 3.26 with the description of moderately implemented this means both public and private school were implemented to their students, the items number 9 can master state-defined content standards in core academic subjects were the mean of 3.24 with the description of moderately implemented, the items number 2 were stated in an equips knowledge and skills in terms of thinking critically, and solving complex problems were the mean of 3.21 with the description of moderately implemented means this items are same to the public and private school in terms of implementation of strategies in students learning, items number 7 were is the recognize capacity to learn and recall information, ideas reactions, and adapt the information to their behavior were the mean of 2.10 with the description of less implemented meaning to say the public and private school are less implemented in terms learning strategies to the students, in items number 8 were the evaluates specific constructs such as linguistic, mechanical, numerical, social, and unique skills included in general mental ability tests were the mean of 2.09 with the description of less implemented meaning to say the respondents less implemented the public and private school in their students in terms of mental ability of the students.

And the items number 10 and 9 were stated in capacitate mental ability in terms of ideas and comprehend abstract problems and improves in academic performance in terms of analytic were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented meaning to say the respondents implied in this items public and private school teachers are less implemented in learners ability.

According to learning of support stated that improved motivation, low self-confidence can make a child feel like her goals and dreams are impossible to reach- or that she is unworthy of achieving those dreams. These feelings will make it difficult for her/his to maintain a high level of dedication and motivation. However, if you help a child build her confidence by teaching her to take small steps towards her goals, she will feel a sense of accomplishment will keep her moving forward when the going gets tough. (RRL page 42 on learning support).

In this table 13 shows that in the self-esteem were the highest mean in the item number rating by the respondents in public school were the number 8 and 4 in participates in educational activities that are interesting and more participatory, and promote the development of self-esteem by offering self-esteem- building activities, were the mean of 3.27, meaning the public teachers were implemented in self-

esteem of the students, in the items number promotes academic achievement, there only a modest correlation between self-esteem and academic performance, were mean of 3.26 were moderately implemented as description given by the respondents.

Table 13. *Students' Development In Terms Of Self-Esteem*

<i>Self-Esteem</i> <i>The teachers observe the learners that...</i>	<i>Public</i> <i>School</i> <i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private</i> <i>School</i> <i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Intensifies the learning success and the positive characteristics	3.24	Moderately Implemented	3.24	Moderately Implemented
2. Improves academic performance.	2.01	Less Implemented	2.03	Less Implemented
3. Claims to be an attraction to have better relationships and make a better impression on other people.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
4. Promote the development of self-esteem by offering self-esteem- building activities.	3.27	Moderately Implemented	3.28	Moderately Implemented
5. Engage in role model activities that demonstrate the ability and disposition of effect change and increase self-esteem.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.02	Less Implemented
6. Develop a sense of accomplishment, a sense of appropriateness, self-confidence, senses of mental of independence, and control of mental tasks in the school curriculum.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.01	Less Implemented
7. Accept the opportunity to discuss and share their ideas.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
8. Participates in educational activities that are interesting and more participatory	3.27	Moderately Implemented	3.28	Moderately Implemented
9. Motivates themselves to academic success as they can shape their future goals and expectations according to their abilities and interests.	2.02	Less Implemented	2.01	Less Implemented
10. Promotes academic achievement, there only a modest correlation between self-esteem and academic performance.	3.26	Moderately Implemented	3.27	Moderately Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.507	Less Implemented	2.514	Less Implemented

In the item number 1 were is the intensifies the learning success and the positive characteristics were the mean of 3.24 with the description of moderately implemented and the item number 9 were the motivates themselves to academic success as they can shape their future goals and expectations according to their abilities and interests were the mean of 2.02, in the item number 2 were are in an improves academic performance were the mean of 2.01 were the description of less implemented meaning to say the public school teacher did not focus on this items in teaching strategies when you comes in self-esteem of the students, in the items number 5, 3, 6 and 7 an engage in role model activities that demonstrate the ability and disposition of effect change and increase self-esteem, claims to be an attraction to have better relationships and make a better impression on other people, accept the opportunity to discuss and share their ideas, and develop a sense of accomplishment, a sense of appropriateness, self-confidence, senses of mental of independence, and control of mental tasks in the school curriculum were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented in terms of self-esteem of the teaching strategies of the teachers'.

According to self- esteem was stated many beliefs you hold about yourself today reflect messages you've received from these people over time. If your relationships are strong and you receive generally positive feedback, you're more likely to see yourself as worthwhile and have healthier self-esteem. If you receive mostly negative feedback and are often criticized, teased or devalued by others, you're more likely to struggle with poor self-esteem. Promote the development of self-esteem by offering self-esteem- building activities and engage in role model activities that demonstrate the ability and disposition of effect change and increase self-esteem. Motivates themselves to academic success as they can shape their future goals and expectations according to their abilities and interests promotes academic achievement, there only a modest correlation between self-esteem and academic performance. (Pages 44 in RRL of this study)

In the private school in the item number 8 and 4 terms of participates in educational activities that are interesting and more participatory and promote the development of self-esteem by offering self-esteem- building activities were got highest mean of 3.28 with the description of moderately implemented in this item both public and private school are implemented in teaching strategies of the teachers in terms of self-esteem of students.

In the item number 10 promotes academic achievement, there only a modest correlation between self-esteem and academic performance were got second highest of mean of 3.27 with the description of moderately implemented it means the teachers observed the learners in self-esteem of the learners both public and private school, in the item number 1 stated that intensifies the learning success and the positive characteristics were got the mean of 3. 24 with the description of moderately implemented meaning the public and private school were implemented, in the items number 2 and 5 stated that improves academic performance and engage in role model activities that demonstrate the ability and disposition of effect change and increase self-esteem were got the mean of 2.03 and 2.02 with the description of less implemented meaning public and private school are not observable by the teachers in implemented in self-esteem in students development, in the item number 6 and 9 were stated that develop a sense of accomplishment, a sense of appropriateness,

self-confidence, senses of mental of independence, and control of mental tasks in the school curriculum and motivates themselves to academic success as they can shape their future goals and expectations according to their abilities and interests were got the mean of 2.01 with the description of less implemented meaning to say that public and private school were not observable apply by the teacher in self-esteem in terms of students' development of the learners, accept the opportunity to discuss and share their ideas.

In the items number 3 is the last item that not observable by the teachers in private school both them that stated and claims to be an attraction to have better relationships and make a better impression on other people were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented.

In this table the private school were focus on the activities and participating activities to promote development of self-esteem of the students according to the study by Robert M. Yerkers and John D. Dodson (1908) revealed that arousal-characterized by the anxiety often brought on by challenges-can increase performance levels, but only to a point. When that point is exceeded, performance decreases. By learning to comfortable while being uncomfortable, students can better cope with the stress that comes when they venture into unfamiliar territory.

Table 14. *Students' Development In Terms Of Skills Competency*

<i>Skills Competency The teachers observe the learners that...</i>	<i>Public School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Private School Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Applies a range of related knowledge, skills, and attitudes to complete a task according to its standards in a defined work area.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.02	Less Implemented
2. Access various technological resources and tools, such as email, internet browsers, LMSs, text and video chat applications, and productivity software and applications.	3.28	Moderately Implemented	3.29	Moderately Implemented
3. Plans and control themselves in the learning process.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
4. Organize their learning activities to contribute to their academic achievement	3.33	Moderately Implemented	3.34	Moderately Implemented
5. Increase motivation and improve academic performance	2.02	Less Implemented	2.01	Less Implemented
6. Improves intrinsic motivation and improve academic performance.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.0	Less Implemented
7. Develops a positive learning attitude and good study habits.	3.29	Moderately Implemented	3.28	Moderately Implemented
8. Influence on the effectiveness of the teachers' teaching and students' learning.	2.0	Less Implemented	2.01	Less Implemented
9. Creates and develops respectful relationships and a sense of community among other learners	3.29	Moderately Implemented	3.28	Moderately Implemented
10. Facilitates and maintains interactive discussion and information exchange.	2.01	Less Implemented	2.02	Less Implemented
Weighted Mean:	2.617	Moderately Implemented	2.604	Moderately Implemented
Overall Mean Public School:		2.657		Moderately Implemented
Overall Mean Private School:		2.846		Moderately Implemented

The table 14 shows the skills competency were in the items stated that the mean of the following based on the result of given by the respondents in accordance with highest to lowest rating, as noted, in public school in the number 4 were stated that organize their learning activities to contribute to their academic achievement were the highest mean of 3.33 with the description of moderately implemented meaning in public school were observable in development of the skills competency of the students' development. In the item number 7 and 9 were stated that develops a positive learning attitude and good study habits and creates and develops respectful relationships and a sense of community among other learners were the mean of 3.29 with the description of moderately implemented in teachers observe the learners in skills competency in learning skills.

In the item number 2 were are stated in an access various technological resources and tools, such as email, internet browsers, LMSs, text and video chat applications, and productivity software and applications were the mean of 3.28 were the description of moderately implemented, and the item number 5 and 10 stated that increase motivation and improve academic performance and facilitates and maintains interactive discussion and information exchange were the mean of 2.02 and 2.01 with the description of less implemented meaning to say the teachers of public school were less observable in skills competency of the students' development.

In the items number 3, 8, 6 and 1 were stated in plans and control themselves in the learning process, influence on the effectiveness of the teachers' teaching and students' learning, improves intrinsic motivation and improve academic performance, and applies a range of related knowledge, skills, and attitudes to complete a task according to its standards in a defined work area meaning the public school less implemented observable in terms of skills competency were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented. Therefore, the public school were focus on the learning activities to contribute to their academic achievement of the students in skills competency through students' development.

In the private school, in this table shows that item number 4 is the highest rating given by the respondents were they stated as an organize their learning activities to contribute to their academic achievement were the mean of 3.34 with the description of moderately implemented meaning to say that public and private school were implemented the skills competency of the students' development in learning.

In the items number 2 were stated an access various technological resources and tools, such as email, internet browsers, LMSs, text and video chat applications, and productivity software and applications were the mean of 3.29 with the description of moderately implemented and the items number 7 and 9 were stated in creates and develops respectful relationships and a sense of community among other learners and develops a positive learning attitude and good study habits were the mean of 3.28 with the description of moderately implemented.

In the items number 1 and 4 were stated as an applies a range of related knowledge, skills, and attitudes to complete a task according to its standards in a defined work area and facilitates and maintains interactive discussion and information exchange were the mean of 2.02 with the description of less implemented meaning the private school were not focus on this statement in terms of skills competency of the students learning or did not observable strategies to the students.

In the items numbers 5 and 8 were stated that increase motivation and improve academic performance and influence on the effectiveness of the teachers' teaching and students' learning were the mean of 2.01 with the description of less implemented the private school and public school are less focus in skills competency of the students' development in terms of strategies learning of the students.

And the in the item number 3, 6 were stated that plans and control themselves in the learning process, improves intrinsic motivation and improve academic performance were the mean of 2.0 with the description of less implemented. According to confidence in knowledge depends on what expects know according to Art Markman, Ph.D. (2016 Psychology today). If we had a way to go into your head and pull out your knowledge, we could figure out objectively whether you actually understand how things in your world work. Unfortunately, there is no way to do that, instead, you have to make judgments about how well you understand the world around you.

Conclusions

The level of teaching performance of the teachers' in public and private school are mostly alike in terms of teachers' strategies and students' development were are moderately implemented in Maguindanao 1 and 2 province for the school year 2021 -2022. This result were based on the overall mean were the public is 2.657 and private is 2.846 means were moderately implemented.

In flexible instruction in teachers' strategies were the public school are less implemented therefore, need to adopt and practice those strategies for the students development.

In self-Esteem in students' development were the public and private school are les implemented. Self-esteem encompasses beliefs about oneself as well as emotional states, such as triumph, despair, pride, and shame. Therefore, we looking forward in adopt and practice of students' development. According to their abilities and interests promotes academic achievement, there only a modest correlation between self-esteem and academic performance. According to Markman in Psychology, 2022.

Teachers as part of their job must examine test result of their students to discover teaching strategies so that they could be used to improve instructional delivery and learning in the school system.

The school be provided by appropriate scientific interventions in terms of sustainable training to develop the capacity building and enhancement of faculty productivity to cope with the new trend in learning strategies to improve and maximize the teaching – learning process.

The teachers learned and practice the flexible instruction strategies and adopt some strategies for the students' development.

A similar study should be replicated using the different variables that would affect and enhance students learning capabilities particular in adopting learning styles and others strategies that will be ready to apply in learning skills and also in same variables that influence the academic performance of the students in learning.

Furthermore, study related to this for the development and acquiring knowledge of the reading and incoming researcher.

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